

RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF ORGANIC MONO-FILAMENTS AFTER COMPRESSIVE LOADING

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1 Introduction

Organic fibers, such as aramid, polyethylene or polyarylate fibers, have great mechanical properties especially under tensile loading. However, under compressive loading, both modulus and strength of these fibers showed drastic decrease comparing to tensile properties. Compressed organic fibers showed typical kink band, which occurs in both macroscopic fiber bundle level and microscopic filament level. Kink band is a local buckling, and therefore residual strength of fiber is possibly affected by the formation of kink band. For aramid fibers, some researchers reported the effect of formation of kink band on the mechanical properties [1,3]. For example, DeTeresa et al. [1] reported that the residual strength of aramid fiber after kink band formation. However, there is no such report about polyarylate fiber, which is an encouraging organic fiber as well as aramid. In this study, the compressive durability of mono-filament of polyarylate fiber was evaluated. Especially, the residual tensile strength was evaluated after static and cyclic compressive loading. The mechanism of degradation of residual strength after compressive loading was discussed with both experimental results and theoretical discussions.

2 Materials and testing methods

2.1 Materials

Polyarylate fibers (VectranTM, Kuraray Co., Ltd.; abbreviated as PA fibers) were examined. The filament diameter was 17 μ m (2.8dtex).

2.2 Testing Methods

Compression test of mono-filament was conducted as follows; 3 filaments were bonded at the center surface of polycarbonate plate, which dimension was 150mm in length, 12mm in width and 3mm in

thickness. The gap between adjacent filaments was 1mm. Each filament was bonded to polycarbonate plate by polyvinyl alcohol glue, which could be removed by water so that residual tensile strength was measured [1]. Compressive strain was applied to mono-filaments by applying three-point bending load to the polycarbonate plate on which mono-filaments were bonded, as shown in Fig. 1.

Firstly, the minimum compressive strain to initiate kink band was measured in static compressive (bending) test of mono-filament. Hereinafter, this strain was called as the critical compressive strain (ε_c) [1].

The distribution of compressive strain on the surface of polycarbonate plate is defined as Eq. 1, and is illustrated in Fig. 1.

$$\varepsilon_c = \frac{P(L/2 - l_c)}{2ZE} \quad (1)$$

Here, P is the load applied to polycarbonate plate, L is the span length between fulcrums, Z is the modulus of section and E is the modulus of polycarbonate. The length between the loading point and the location of the farthest kink band from the loading point is defined as the critical compressive span, l_c .

Compressive strain levels in fatigue test were 50%, 100% and 150% of the ε_c . Residual tensile strength was measured after 1 cycle (static test), 10^3 cycles, 10^4 cycles, 10^5 cycles and 10^6 cycles. Frequency of fatigue test was 5 Hz.

Tensile test of mono-filament conformed to Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS) R 7606. Gage length of specimen was 60mm as shown in Fig. 2, and testing speed was 1.0mm/min. Testing machine used was the compact table-top universal testing machine (EZ Test, Shimadzu Corporation) which capacity of a scale was 5N.

In advance of tensile test, diameter of filament was observed and measured by the digital microscope (VHX-500, Keyence Corporation) in order to obtain accurate modulus and strength.

Fig. 1 Illustration of compressive strain distribution caused by three-point bending.

Fig. 2 Specimen for tensile test of monofilament.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Critical compressive strain

Static compressive tests of mono-filament were conducted with 60mm and 100mm of fulcrum span, respectively, in order to evaluate the effect of fulcrum span on critical compressive strain, ϵ_c . ϵ_c was 0.55% (standard deviation (SD): 0.13) for 60mm of fulcrum span and 0.58% (SD: 0.12) for 100mm of fulcrum span. Therefore the effect of fulcrum span is very small.

3.2 Residual tensile strength

Fig. 3 shows the relationship between residual strength and the number of cycles in PA mono-

filament. The specimens applied the strain of $0.5\epsilon_c$ showed almost same value of residual tensile strength as intact specimens. The number of cycles in which decrease of tensile strength started was 10^5 cycles for specimens applied the strain of $1.0\epsilon_c$ and $1.5\epsilon_c$. Especially, the residual strength of specimens applied $1.5\epsilon_c$ decreased in 28% of intact filament at 10^6 cycles. Therefore, it was supposed that the dependency of cycle number on residual strength was large.

Figure 4 shows microphotographs at fracture point of PA mono-filament after residual tensile strength test. These photographs show the specimens in which different conditions of compressive fatigue were applied as follows; (a) intact, (b) $1.0\epsilon_c$ for 10^4 cycles, (c) $1.5\epsilon_c$ for 10^4 cycles, (d) $1.0\epsilon_c$ for 10^5 cycles, (e) $1.5\epsilon_c$ for 10^5 cycles and (f) $1.0\epsilon_c$ for 10^6 cycles.

Photographs in Fig.4 (a), (b) and (c) showed typical fibrillation failure. Combined with the result of residual tensile strength, it is found that the effect of the number of cycles was little up to 10^4 .

A part of filament showed fibrillation but another part showed brittle failure in Fig.4 (d). This failure morphology indicates that a filament gradually failed from the part of kink band weakened by compression.

No fibrillation and flat fracture surface was observed at the fracture point in the specimens shown in Fig.4 (e), (f) and (g). These fracture surfaces is supposed to be corresponded to the location of kink bands. It is supposed this brittle fracture morphology caused drastic decrease of residual tensile strength.

Fig. 3 Residual tensile strength.

Fig. 4 Microphotographs at fracture point of PA mono-filament after residual tensile strength test.

Discussions

Budiansky et al [4,5] reported that kink band initiated in the compressed composite materials depends on the shear yield stress. The initiation stress of kink band is expressed by shear yield stress τ_Y and strain γ_Y of composites and initial misalignment of fiber $\bar{\phi}$, all which are shown in Fig. 5, as following equation:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{\tau_Y}{\gamma_Y + \bar{\phi}} = \frac{G}{1 + \bar{\phi}/\gamma_Y} \quad (2)$$

Here, the right hand of this equation is the expression by using of shear modulus of composites, G .

If we use "fibrils" as a substitute for "fibers", we can extend this equation to the initiation stress of kink band of mono-filament. When the fiber having fibrillar structures yields under shear stress, it is assumed that chemical bondings between adjacent fibrils are broken. Thus, it is supposed that the shear yield stress of organic fiber is one of the parameters expressing bonding force between fibrils. In this study, we discussed the shear yield stress, which may affect initiation of kink band of organic fibers, based on Budiansky's equation.

Fig. 5 Kink band geometry and notation [4].

Fig. 6 An expanded structural model of the thermotropic and lyotropic LCPs [2].

As shown in Fig. 4 and also Fig. 6 which is an illustration drawn by Sawyer et al [2], PA filaments have skin-core structure, in which comparably thick skin layer exists on the surface of a filament. However kink bands could be observed with light transmission method by using optical microscope, it was difficult to observe kink band under scanning electron microscope because kink band mainly occurred beneath skin layer. Thus, at the current moment, we could not observe rotation angle ϕ of PA fibers.

Therefore, we discussed here the initiation stress of kink band by using of aramid fibers (Kevlar®29, Du Pont; abbreviated as K29), which is also an organic fiber and was easily observed by scanning electron microscope.

Firstly, we discussed the applicability of Eq. 1 to mono-filament. We experimentally measured the critical compressive strain of K29 as well as PA fibers, and calculated initiation stress of kink band by using of elastic modulus. On the other hand, the initiation stress of kink band was estimated based on Eq. 1. We compared these two kink band initiation stresses.

The critical compressive strain ε_c of K29 was experimentally measured by the same method as PA fibers, and we obtained about 0.01. Because the tensile modulus of K29 is 71GPa, then the initial stress of kink band, $\sigma_{c,exp}$, was 0.71GPa. Rotation angle of kink band, ϕ , in K29 mono-filament was measured in images of scanning electron microscope, as shown in Fig.7. We obtained average value of ϕ as 6.7° ($= 0.117$ as shear strain expression).

Here, we focused on the right hand of Eq. 1. However shear modulus G of K29 is unknown, that of Kevlar®49 (K49) was experimentally measured by Tsai et al [6]. We assumed that shear modulus is proportional to tensile modulus, and we can estimate G of K29 is 8.9GPa. If we put shear yield strain, γ_Y , equals to critical compressive strain $\varepsilon_c = 0.01$, then the initial stress of kink band, $\sigma_{c,th}$, was 0.70GPa. This $\sigma_{c,th}$ shows good agreement with $\sigma_{c,exp}$ and the result by DeTerasa et al. (however, result for K49) [1]. Here, shear yield stress, τ_Y , is derived from Eq. 1 as 89MPa. Validity of this value will be discussed in the future.

On the other hand, Budiansky et al. [5] suggested that the fracture of fiber does not influence σ_c , and

fiber rotation angle at fiber fracture, $\phi_{fracture}$, is approximated as follows:

$$\phi_{fracture} \approx \left(\frac{2\tau_Y}{E} \right)^{1/3} \quad (2)$$

When both shear yield stress τ_Y derived above and tensile modulus of K29, 71GPa, are applied to this equation, then $\phi_{fracture}$ is 0.136 ($= 7.7^\circ$). This rotation angle is close to the observed value (6.7°).

Therefore, it was confirmed that the Budiansky's equation could be applicable to mono-filaments. We will observe rotation angle of kink band of PA and discuss the bonding force between fibrils of PA based on the shear yield stress derived from Budiansky's equation.

Fig. 7 Initial kink band in a K29 filament.

4 Conclusions and Future Outlook

This study focused on the micro-level buckling phenomenon, so called kink band, in a polyarylate mono-filament. The initiation strain and the residual tensile strength of post-kinked filament were experimentally evaluated.

- (1) It was found that kink band occurred at about 0.5% of strain. The residual tensile strength after cyclic compressive load drastically decreased over 10^5 cycles. As increasing compressive cycles, tensile failure mode changed from fibrillation failure to brittle failure at kink band.
- (2) We assumed that the shear yield stress of organic fiber is one of the parameters expressing bonding force between fibrils. We validated the theory of kink band initiation stress derived by Budiansky et al. by means of Kevlar®29 fibers. Theoretical kink band initiation stress showed

good agreement with that obtained experimentally. Further discussions will be conducted about the validity of shear yield stress obtained.

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